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DEVELOPMENT OF DISTANCE EDUCATION IN RUSSIA

**Zhdanova, Tatiana Alekseevna¹, Kashirsky, Sergey Nikolaevich²,
Makarova, Anna Anatolievna³**

¹Candidate of Philological Sciences, Associate Professor, Voronezh State Technical University,
84, 20-Let Oktyabrya Street, Voronezh, Russia, E-mail: zhdanovsilver@mail.ru

²Candidate of Pedagogical Sciences, Associate Professor, Voronezh State Technical University,
84, 20-Let Oktyabrya Street, Voronezh, Russia, E-mail: dream-school@mail.ru

³Candidate of Philological Sciences, Associate Professor, Voronezh State Technical University,
84, 20-Let Oktyabrya Street, Voronezh, Russia, E-mail: annasaborovskaja2017@mail.ru

Abstract

The article discusses some aspects of modern distance education, which is developing against the background of globalization processes that impose new requirements on the subject of any field of activity, where the basic skills are: the ability to navigate the array of incoming information, the ability to act in conditions of lack of necessary data, the ability to create new information flows based on the information received and analyzed. Special attention is paid to the modern specialist, who requires constant updating of acquired knowledge and skills, which allows us to talk about the transition from the concept of "education for life" to the concept of "education through life".

Keywords: education, people, society, power, history, computer.

I. INTRODUCTION

The Russian system of higher education has a fundamental scientific base that makes it possible to prepare a comprehensively developed graduate, but the onset of the information age and globalization in education require its modernization, the application of new approaches to organizing the activities of higher education. Classical teaching methods (learning using paper textbooks, traditional lectures, seminars, etc.) do not fully use the full potential of information technology in education, available to teachers and students today. Often, when using traditional teaching methods, students receive outdated information that does not correspond well to modern realities, which cannot become the basis for future professional activities. The importance of solving the problem of matching the level of higher education with the trends of the time is determined by the powerful influence of this institution on the formation of personality, social groups, the spiritual, moral, and economic potential of society, on the success of a person's adaptation in the modern globalizing world.

This necessitates the modernization of higher education, the development of innovative areas of education that combine flexibility, scalability, convenience of obtaining knowledge, accessibility for the student, based on modern information technologies, capable of meeting the needs of students in obtaining up-to-date information for professional and personal growth, which, in ultimately, and is an objectively necessary condition for the entry of Russian higher education into the global educational space.

II. METHODOLOGY

The information base for the article was the legal documents on higher education in the Russian Federation, official statistics, the results of research by domestic and foreign historians in the field of distance higher education, Russian and international resources of the global Internet. In the process of writing, common general scientific methods were used, such as analogy, analysis, synthesis. The data were interpreted by grouping, ranking and classification methods, methods of logical, systemic analysis of information and traditional methods of sociological research were also used: document analysis, statistical review, generalization of modern literature, periodicals.

III. RESULTS

In Russia, the date of the official development of distance learning can be considered May 30, 1997, when order No. 1050 of the Ministry of Education of Russia was issued, allowing the experiment of distance learning in the field of education.

There are various ways to organize distance learning based on new information technologies: based on interactive television, telecommunications, based on CD-ROM technologies, educational radio and television, video recording, etc.

In recent years, four types of distance learning based on:

1. Interactive television (two-way TV);
2. Computer telecommunication networks (regional and global, Internet) in the mode of exchanging text files;
3. Computer telecommunication networks using multimedia information, including in interactive mode, as well as using computer videoconferencing;
4. Combination of the first and second.

Education based on interactive television (two-way TV), with all its attractiveness, the possibility of direct visual contact with an audience located at different distances from the teacher, has its drawbacks. The fact is that with such training, the usual lesson is practically replicated, whether it is built according to the traditional method or using modern pedagogical technologies. It is, roughly speaking, about replicating the method used by the teacher with the help of modern technologies. If traditional methods of the class-lesson system with a predominance of frontal types of work are used, then the effect is lower than usual when the lesson is conducted in one class, because the audience increases significantly due to distant students, and hence the attention of the teacher to each individual student decreases by the same amount. At the same time, in the system of advanced training of teaching staff, this form of distance learning can hardly be overestimated, since teachers, students, pupils can become not just third-party witnesses, but also active participants in the use of new pedagogical, information technologies, take part in discussions, etc. This form of distance learning is inherently interactive and, of course, can be considered very promising, if not in the system of mass education, then in the system of advanced training and student training. However, these are still extremely expensive technologies.

Another way to organize distance learning using modern information technologies, as mentioned above, is computer telecommunications in the form of e-mail, teleconferences, other information resources of local networks, as well as the Internet, but only on the basis of textual information. I must say that at present for the vast majority of universities this is the most affordable way to organize distance learning. This method does not provide for the exchange of graphic, sound files, and does not provide for the use of multimedia tools. This is the cheapest way to organize distance learning. The third method of organizing distance learning provides for the use of the latest means of telecommunication technologies, including multimedia, all the possibilities of the Internet, including video and audio conferences, as well as the use of CDs. Distance learning is designed for the category of people who, due to objective reasons, cannot use the traditional form of education. These categories include, for example, citizens with disabilities, people who need to combine education and work or live in regions of Russia where there are not enough educational institutions comparable to those in the capital or international, as well as women in Muslim countries who are prohibited from visit public places, etc. In addition, distance learning is used by citizens who want to study at prestigious universities in Russia or the world, but do not have sufficient financial resources or time. The main advantage of education based on communication technologies is: non-competitive admission; independent planning of time and pace of classes; lack of fixed terms of training; the ability to study at home and through any computer connected to the Internet; access to world resources, virtual libraries and databases. Recruitment for distance learning is carried out throughout the year. In addition, the presence of a personal teacher-curator allows you to better master the material being studied, and on special forums there is an opportunity to discuss topics and ideas with other students. Thus, the issue of student isolation, as it might seem at first glance, is not relevant in this form of education. The popularity of distance education, in addition to the development of technology, is directly related to the increase in the cost of full-time education. The cost of online education is much lower, in addition, it varies depending on the specialty, the form of the training program and the type of educational institution. In addition, there are also various educational grants and scholarship programs that allow you to study remotely for free or with partial funding. Moreover, in this case, there are no expenses for a flight to the country of study, for accommodation, meals, medical insurance, etc. Distance learning helps to bypass psychological barriers associated with a person's communicative qualities, such as shyness, fear of public speaking.

University readiness for distance learning during COVID-19 Russia 2020.

The realities of modern Russia are such that many groups of the population today do not have the opportunity to use modern communication technologies for financial and other reasons. The technical equipment in Russia is significantly inferior to the leading countries of the world. In addition, a person who wants to study remotely must have knowledge of computer technologies and programs.

Number of users of online education in Russia from 2017 to 2027, by segment.

Not the last factor for the successful receipt of distance education is the personal characteristics of the individual. It is no secret that in the absence of daily control, as is customary with traditional full-time education, it is necessary to have a clear motivation. Undoubtedly, social interaction in the form of a live exchange of ideas, experiences, psychological support of the group and the moment of competition in the remote form have been lost to some extent. That is why this form of education is less suitable for people who do not have the personal qualities of self-organization and discipline. Distance learning is more suitable for education in the field of fundamental sciences, humanities or technology.

Technical specialties, in comparison with the humanities, are less in demand with this form of education, since mastering them requires a large amount of practical and laboratory work. Distance education via the Internet is not just a convenient form of education, but also a serious alternative to the traditional form in the future. According to the American Educational Research Association, by 2026, about two-thirds of the world's students will be studying remotely.

Percentage of higher education students taking open, online or distance education courses.

It should be noted that for Russia the relevance and necessity of distance learning is associated with a number of factors. Among them are vast territories and the concentration of scientific and technical centers in large cities, the formation of new needs of the population in relation to the content and technologies of education, the development of a market economy, and increased migration of the population.

IV. CONCLUSION

Speaking of distance learning, we mean a completely different educational technology, and it is not entirely correct to compare teaching methods in full-time and distance learning. And part of the myths is precisely related to the fact that people unconsciously (or very consciously) try to combine their traditional ideas about educational processes with new realities. And finally, no one is going to replace all full-time education with distance education. Distance education should become an equal form of meeting educational needs, the same as full-time, correspondence or external education. Unfortunately, distance learning methods have not yet become widespread. There are many reasons for this, both objective (lack of legal support, teaching technologies) and subjective (the traditional mentality of students and teachers, concerns about the effectiveness of distance learning).

However, the experience of introducing high-quality distance learning into the system of higher education in Russia shows that specialists who have acquired knowledge in this way are not inferior in qualification to traditional methods.

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РАЗВИТИЕ ДИСТАНЦИОННОГО ОБРАЗОВАНИЯ В РОССИИ

**Жданова Татьяна Алексеевна¹, Каширский Сергей Николаевич²,
Макарова Анна Анатольевна³**

¹Кандидат филологических наук, доцент, Воронежский государственный технический университет, ул. 20-летия Октября, 84, Воронеж, Россия, E-mail: zhdanovsilver@mail.ru

²Кандидат педагогических наук, доцент, Воронежский государственный технический университет, ул. 20-летия Октября, 84, Воронеж, Россия, E-mail: dream-school@mail.ru

³Кандидат филологических наук, доцент, Воронежский государственный технический университет, ул. 20-летия Октября, 84, Воронеж, Россия, E-mail: annasaborowskaja2017@mail.ru

Аннотация

В статье рассматриваются некоторые аспекты современного дистанционного образования, которое развивается на фоне процессов глобализации, предъявляющих новые требования к субъекту любой сферы деятельности, где базовыми навыками являются: умение ориентироваться в массиве поступающей информации, умение действовать в условиях отсутствия необходимых данных, способность создавать новые информационные потоки на основе полученной и проанализированной информации. Особое внимание уделено современному специалисту, которому требуется постоянное обновление полученных знаний и умений, что позволяет говорить о переходе от концепции "образование на всю жизнь" к концепции "образование через всю жизнь".

Ключевые слова: образование, люди, общество, власть, история, компьютер.

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